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Human Resources Management As a Determination of Star Hotel Performance in Indonesia

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Abstract

Indonesia has various types of industries, one of which is the hospitality service industry. The room occupancy rate in hotels, especially the star ones, decreased for 2016-2020. This was caused by the less effective and not optimum implementation of human resources (HR) management, the HR recruited were less competent in their field and unsuitably placed in some positions, lacking motivation, guidance, and supervision to carry out their duties. These problems affected the HR performance and decreased work productivity. Consequently, the hotel performance also decreased due to not maximum services provided to tourists. Another effect was the room occupancy rates in hotels, especially star hotels tended to decline. This research employed descriptive quantitative through path analysis using SPSS 22. The population of this study included 7,021 employees working in five-star hotels in Indonesia. By purposive sampling technique, 100 employees of the population were taken as the samples. The study results based on the partial hypothesis showed that the variables of HR planning, HR organization, and work supervision for employees had a positive and significant effect on the work productivity of star hotel employees in Indonesia, and these three variables affected the performance of star hotels in Indonesia. Simultaneously, the variables of HR planning, HR organizing, and work supervision had a positive and significant impact on the performance of star hotels in Indonesia through the work productivity of the star hotel employees in Indonesia.

Keyword : *hr planning, hr organizing, giving motivation, work supervision, work productivity*

1. INTRODUCTION

All economic activities can generate maximum profit. When an entity or business in the economic field continues to move, the business must be well organized to increase its efforts and productivity in yielding maximum profits. A business must be organized continuously and comprehensively. The business owners should be able to properly organize the activities within the company, while the purpose of organizing is enhancing company productivity and performance in generating maximum profit. Therefore, company owners must implement human resources management properly. It means the business owners must carry out HR planning carefully, organize the organization within the company properly, recruit and place people based on their positions and competencies, guide and provide good motivation to employees to make them enthusiastic and productive, and carry out efficient and effective supervision to ensure that the recruited HR work the company's visions and missions or the established SOPs. Indonesia has various kinds of companies, both manufacturing and service industries. One of the developing businesses in the service sector is the hotel industry. The hotel industry is related to maximum service in serving visiting guests. This maximum service can increase the company's ability to generate maximum profit. The hospitality service industry in Indonesia has implemented human resource management. This is evidenced by the large number of HR recruited and placed in various positions in hotels. In 2016-2020, the number of HR recruited increased. Those employees support hotels in executing their operational activities and ultimately reaching maximum profit. The increasing number of hospitality workforces in Indonesia for the last five years is presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Number of Hospitality Workforces in Indonesia for 2016-2020

No	Year	The Number of Hospitality Workforces in Indonesia (People)	The Number of Hospitality Workforces Absorbed in Star Hotels in Indonesia (People)
1	2016	6,251,257	5,680
2	2017	6,904,745	6,557
3	2018	7,766,077	6,747
4	2019	8,562,226	7,781
5	2020	8,543,794	7,021

Source: The Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy RI, 2020

Based on Table 1, the number of workers in the hospitality industry continued to grow, yet the number of workforces absorbed in the star hotels continued to decline. This decrease was due to the difficulty of the star hotels in finding competent human resources to be placed in the company. In other words, the implementation of HR management in star hotels should be improved. This can be seen from the decrease in the number of guests or tourists, especially local tourists staying at five-star hotels. The overview of the demand for star hotel occupancy rates in Indonesia in 2016-2020 is displayed in Table 2.

Table 2 Rate of Star Hotel Occupancy by Tourists Visiting Indonesia for 2016-2020

Year	The Rate of Hotel Room Occupancy by Tourists Visiting the Hotels in di Indonesia (People)	The Rate of Star Hotel Room Occupancy by Tourists Visiting the Hotels in Indonesia (People)	Percentage of The Rate of Star Hotel Room Occupancy by Tourists (%)
2016	11,095,000	6,268,675	56.50
2017	14,075,832	8,379,343	59.53
2018	14,612,466	8,730,948	59.75
2019	16,106,954	9,565,920	59.39
2020	4,052,923	1,653,187	40.79

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics, 2020

Based on Table 2, there was a decrease in the room occupancy rate in hotels, especially the star ones, for 2016-2020. This was caused by the less effective and not optimum implementation of human resource management. The HR recruited were less competent in their field and improperly placed in some positions, lacking motivation, guidance, and good supervision to carry out their duties. Therefore, the workers' performance and work productivity tended to decrease and thus affected the hotel performance, where the services provided to tourists were not maximum. Ultimately, the room occupancy rates in hotels, especially the star ones tended to decline as well.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. HR Planning

Kang, et al (2019), HR planning is a management process that is carried out starting from planning the procurement of human resources, the recruitment process, training and human resource development. Aguiar-Quintana, et al (2020) HR planning is a human resource procurement process that is carried out systematically in order to meet the needs of positions and organizations in order to achieve the goals that have been set. Mcphail, et al (2008) HR planning in the tourism industry including hospitality is a series of HR procurement processes that are in accordance with the needs in the hospitality industry where the HR recruitment process is carried out in accordance with their competencies, organizing, to training and developing human resources.

2.2. HR Organizing

Dai, et al (2019), HR organization is a process of placing HR into certain positions their competencies. Karatepe, et al (2018), HR organization is the process of regulating and dividing HR into strategic positions and in accordance with the organizational structure. Maarif, et al (2019), organization in several companies,

especially in the hospitality industry, must be carried out in accordance with the competencies and expertise possessed by each HR who will be placed into the organizational structure.

2.3. Giving Motivation

Hanggraeni (2012) motivation is a process of giving encouragement and encouragement to employees so that employees can work optimally and help the company achieve its goals. Agarwal (2020) providing motivation is an activity to provide encouragement and strong mentality to employees so that they can work established procedures, so that they can increase their work productivity. Hsiao, et al (2018), management provides motivation in the hospitality industry with the intention that employees can work to serve customers to the maximum possible so that hotel performance increases and goals or objectives can be achieved.

2.4. Work Supervision

Kim, et al (2020) work supervision is a process of monitoring and controlling the work of employees which is intended so that the work of employees is in accordance with what has been determined by the company. Mohsin, et al (2015) work supervision is a management activity carried out by supervising all employee activities or work whether in accordance with the standards set by the company. Tamsang, et al (2017) work supervision in hotels is carried out so that employees can work the direction and demands of the company and in accordance with what the management wants to work established procedures or paths to serve customers optimally and reduce customer complaints at the hotel when stay overnight.

2.5. Work Productivity

Chan, et al (2019), work productivity is a measuring tool to measure how far the company's performance helps the company in achieving the specified goals. Qu, et al (2021) work productivity is related to employee performance in improving their performance, where the work results can increase the company's ability to achieve the goals set and the results can be obtained to improve employee careers. Hewagam, et al (2019), work productivity in hotels can be measured by how maximal the services provided by employees to hotel customers are, where the maximum that can be measured is reducing customer complaints about the facilities and services provided by employees. Company performance. Larasati (2018), company performance is a process that can measure the extent to which the company can improve its capabilities in order to achieve the goals that have been set. Pereira-Moliner, et al (2021) the company's performance describes how the company's efforts to increase profits are maximized, so that in the coming year they are able to carry out their operational activities better. Ali, et al (2020) the performance of existing hotels can be measured to what extent the hotel can improve its services to the maximum and the extent to which the service is beneficial to customers, so that the hotel as a company can get maximum profit in the future

3. RESEARCH METHOD

This research employed a descriptive quantitative method. Amir, et al (2010), the quantitative descriptive method explains phenomena and problems occurring factually without setting. The quantitative descriptive data analysis was conducted using path analysis, where Rukajat (2015), path analysis is a data analysis used to estimate the relationship between variables. Different from regression analysis, path analysis has intervening variables. The population of this study included 7,021 workforces working in five-star hotels in Indonesia, amounting to people/person, where 100 samples were taken by using the purposive sampling technique. Sukajat (2015) stated that in the purposive sampling technique, the samples are taken based on the conditions occurring. In this research, the samples represented the employees working in five-star hotels in Indonesia with certain characteristics. The samples were randomly selected through questionnaires distributed via Whatsapp.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. The Effects of HR Planning, HR Organizing, Motivating the Employees, and Work Supervising on Star Hotel Performance in Indonesia

4.1.1. Multiple Linear Regression Equation Analysis

Table 3 Multiple Linear Regression Equation Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	15.866	5.361		2.959	.004		
X1 (HR Planning)	.022	.116	.019	3.189	.001	.966	1.035
X2 (HR Organizing)	.105	.103	.102	-.026	.308	.972	1.029
X3 (Motivating the Employees)	-.003	.111	-.003	4.026	.002	.995	1.005
X4 (Work Supervision)	.274	.102	.264	2.675	.000	.991	1.009

a. Dependent Variable: Y

Source: Data Processing (SPSS), 2020

Based on Table 3, the result of linear regression equation is as follow:

$$Y = 15.866 + 0.022X_1 + 0.105X_2 - 0.003X_3 + 0.274X_4$$

The value of regression coefficient X_1 for the HR planning is 0.022. It showed that HR planning had a positive and significant effect on the star hotel performance in Indonesia, where the better the HR planning carried out by star hotels in Indonesia, their performance increased by 0.022%. The value of the regression coefficient X_2 for the HR organizing is 0.105. It indicated that the HR organizing had a positive and significant effect on the star hotel performance in Indonesia, where the better the HR organizing in star hotels in Indonesia, their performance enhanced by 0.105%. The value of the regression coefficient X_3 for motivating the employees is -0.003. It meant that motivating the employees had a negative effect on the star hotel performance in Indonesia, where the more motivation provided to star hotel employees, the star hotel performance in Indonesia decreased by 0.003%. The value of the regression coefficient X_4 for the work supervision is 0.274. It showed the work supervision had a positive and significant effect on the star hotel performance in Indonesia, where the better the work supervision carried out by star hotel management in Indonesia, the star hotel performance improved by 0.274%.

4.1.2. Determination Coefficient (R^2)

Table 4 Results of Determination Coefficient Test

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. Change	
1	.784 ^a	.780	.742	5.35697	.780	2.677	4	95	.000	2.057

a. Predictors: (Constant), X4, X2, X3, X1

b. Dependent Variable: Y

Source: Data Processing (SPSS), 2020

Based on Table 4, the determination coefficient (Adjusted R Square) is 0.742. It showed that 74.2% of the HR planning, HR organizing, motivating the employees, and work supervision significantly impacted the star hotel performance in Indonesia and the remaining 25.8% were influenced by other variables not discussed in this study.

4.1.3. Simultaneous Hypothesis Test

Table 5 Results of Simultaneous Test
ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	238.360	4	59.590	2.677	.090 ^b
	Residual	2726.230	95	28.697		
	Total	2964.590	99			

a. Dependent Variable: Y

b. Predictors: (Constant), X4, X2, X3, X1

Source: Data Processing (SPSS), 2020

Based on Table 5, the F-table value is 2.677 greater than the F-count value of 2.47. IT indicated that simultaneously, the HR planning, HR organizing, motivating the employees, and work supervision had a positive and significant effect on the star hotel performance in Indonesia.

4.1.4. Partial Hypothesis TestTable 6 Results of Partial Test
Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	15.866	5.361		2.959	.004		
X1 (HR Planning)	.022	.116	.019	3.189	.001	.966	1.035
X2 (HR Organizing)	.105	.103	.102	-.026	.308	.972	1.029
X3 (Motivating the Employees)	-.003	.111	-.003	4.026	.002	.995	1.005
X4 (Work Supervision)	.274	.102	.264	2.675	.000	.991	1.009

a. Dependent Variable: Y

Source: Data Processing (SPSS), 2020

Based on Table 6, HR planning, HR organizing, motivating the employees, and work supervision had a positive and significant effect on the star hotel performance in Indonesia. This can be seen from the t-value for those three variables of 3.189, 4.026, and 2.675, respectively, greater than the t-table value of 1.661.

4.2. The Effects of HR Planning, HR Organizing, Motivating the Employees, and Work Supervision on Work Productivity of Star Hotel Employees in Indonesia**4.2.1. Multiple Linear Regression Equation Analysis**Table 7 Multiple Linear Regression Equation
Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	12.362	4.736		2.610	.011		
X1 (HR Planning)	.430	.102	.400	4.206	.000	.966	1.035
X2 (HR Organizing)	.053	.091	.056	2.589	.001	.972	1.029
X3 (Motivating the Employees)	-.022	.098	-.021	-.221	.825	.995	1.005
X4 (Work Supervision)	.024	.090	.025	3.264	.002	.991	1.009

a. Dependent Variable: Z

Source: Data Processing (SPSS), 2020

Based on Table 7, the output of the linear regression equation is as follow:

$$Z = 12.362 + 0.430X_1 + 0.053X_2 - 0.022X_3 + 0.024X_4$$

The value of the regression coefficient X_1 for the HR planning is 0.430. It showed that HR planning had a positive and significant effect on employee work productivity, where the better HR planning carried out by star hotels in Indonesia, the work productivity of the star hotel employees in Indonesia increased by 0.430%. The value of the regression coefficient X_2 for the HR organizing is 0.053. It indicated that HR organizing had a positive and significant effect on employee work productivity, where the better the HR organized is in accordance with the positions and functions, the work productivity of star hotel employees in Indonesia improved by 0.053 %. The value of the regression coefficient X_3 for motivating the employees is - 0.022. It meant that motivating the employees had a negative effect on employee work productivity, where the increased motivation for employees provided by the management of star hotels in Indonesia, the quality of employee work productivity decreased by 0.022%. The value of the regression coefficient X_4 for the employee work supervision is 0.024. It showed that the work supervision had a positive and significant effect on employee work productivity, where the better the work supervision carried out by the star hotel management in Indonesia, the employee work productivity escalated by 0.024%.

4.2.2. Determination Coefficient (R^2)

Table 8 Results of Determination Coefficient

Model Summary ^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. Change	
1	.714 ^a	.772	.737	4.73257	.772	4.923	4	95	.001	1.837

a. Predictors: (Constant), X4, X2, X3, X1

b. Dependent Variable: Z

Source: Data Processing (SPSS), 2020

Table 8 presents the value of the determination coefficient (Adjusted R Square) is 0.737%. It indicated that 73.7% of HR planning, HR organizing, motivating the employees, and work supervision significantly impacted the employee work productivity in the star hotels in Indonesia, while the remaining 26.3% were influenced by other variables excluded from this study.

4.2.3. Simultaneous Hypothesis Test

Table 9 Simultaneous Hypothesis Test

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	441.015	4	110.254	4.923	.001 ^b
	Residual	2127.735	95	22.397		
	Total	2568.750	99			

a. Dependent Variable: Z

b. Predictors: (Constant), X4, X2, X3, X1

Source: Data Processing (SPSS), 2020

Table 9 explains the F value is 4.923 greater than the F-table value of 2.47. It meant that simultaneously, HR planning, HR organizing, motivating the employees, and work supervision positively and significantly affected the work productivity of the star hotel employees in Indonesia.

4.2.4. Partial Hypothesis Test Uji

Table 10 Partial Hypothesis Test Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	12.362	4.736		2.610	.011		
	X1 (HR Planning)	.430	.102	.400	4.206	.000	.966	1.035
	X2 (HR Organizing)	.053	.091	.056	2.589	.001	.972	1.029
	X3 (Motivating the Employees)	-.022	.098	-.021	-.221	.825	.995	1.005
	X4 (Work Supervision)	.024	.090	.025	3.264	.002	.991	1.009

a. Dependent Variable: Z

Source: Data Processing (SPSS), 2020

Table 10 describes that HR planning, HR organizing, and employee work supervision had a positive and significant effect on the work productivity of star hotel employees in Indonesia. This can be seen from the t-value for those three variables of 4.206, 2.589, and 3.264, respectively, greater than the t-table value of 1.661.

4.3. The Effect of Employee Work Productivity on Star Hotel Performance in Indonesia

4.3.1. Simple Linear Regression Equation Analysis

Table 11 Simple Linear Regression Equation Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	25.734	2.890		8.904	.000		
	Z (Star Hotel Performance in Indonesia)	2.021	.108	.020	2.196	.004	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Y

Source: Data Processing (SPSS), 2020

Based on Table 11, the result of the simple regression is as follow:

$$Y = 25.734 + 2.021X_1$$

The value of the regression coefficient Z shows a positive value of 2.021. It indicated that the employee work productivity had a positive and significant effect on the star hotel performance in Indonesia, where the increasing employee productivity would impact on the improving star hotels performance in Indonesia by 2.021%.

Determination Coefficient (R²)

Table 12 Results of Determination Coefficient

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. Change	
1	.820 ^a	.800	.810	5.49900	.700	3.038	1	98	.003	1.857

a. Predictors: (Constant), Z

b. Dependent Variable: Y

Source: Data Processing (SPSS), 2020

Table 12 presents the determination coefficient (Adjusted R Square) value is 0.810 or 81%. It showed that the increase in employee work productivity strongly affected the star hotel performance in Indonesia, while the remaining 19% were influenced by other factors not explained in this study.

4.3.2. Partial Test

Table 13 Results of Partial Test

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	25.734	2.890		8.904	.000		
	Z (Star Hotel Performance in Indonesia)	2.021	.108	.020	2.196	.004	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Y

Source: Data Processing (SPSS), 2020

Table 13 explains that the work productivity of tourism employees positively and significantly affect the star hotel performance in Indonesia. This can be seen from the t-count value of 2.196 greater than the t-table of 1.661.

4.4. The Effects of HR Planning, HR Organizing, Motivating the Employees, and Work Supervision on Star Hotel Performance in Indonesia with Employee Work Productivity as an Intervening Variable

The partial test (t-test) of the first, second, and third substructures resulted in:

$$Y = 0.022X_1 + 0.105X_2 - 0.003X_3 + 0.274X_4 \text{ with a determination coefficient } R^2 = 0.742$$

$$Z = 0.430X_1 + 0.053X_2 - 0.022X_3 + 0.024X_4 \text{ with a determination coefficient } R^2 = 0.737$$

$$Y = 2.021Z \text{ with a determination coefficient } R^2 = 0.810$$

The relationship between the effects of HR planning, HR organizing, motivating the employees, and work supervision on the star hotel performance in Indonesia, with the work productivity of the star hotel employees in Indonesia as an intervening variable can be seen in Table 14.

Table 14 Summary of Direct Effect Research Results

No	The Relationship between Variables	Regression Coefficient Values	Positive/Negative Coefficient	Notes
1	The effect of HR planning on the work productivity of star hotel employees in Indonesia	0.430	Positive	H ₁ was accepted
2	The effect of HR organizing on the work productivity of star hotel employees in Indonesia	0.053	Positive	H ₂ was accepted
3	The effect of motivating the employees on the work productivity of star hotel employees in Indonesia	-0.022	Negative	H ₃ was rejected
4	The effect of work supervision on the work productivity of star hotel employees in Indonesia	0.024	Positive	H ₄ was accepted
5	The effect of HR planning on the star hotel performance in Indonesia	0.022	Positive	H ₅ was accepted
6	The effect of HR organizing on the star hotel performance in Indonesia	0.105	Positive	H ₆ was accepted
7	The effect of motivating the employees on the star hotel performance in Indonesia	-0.003	Negative	H ₇ was rejected
8	The effect of work supervision on the star hotel performance in Indonesia	0.274	Positive	H ₈ was accepted
9	The effect of employee work productivity on the star hotel performance in Indonesia	2.021	Positive	H ₉ was accepted

Source: Data Processing (SPSS), 2020

The relationship between the effect of HR planning on the star hotel performance in Indonesia through the employee work productivity as an intervening variable = $0.430 \times 0.022 \times 2.021 = 0.019$. This result showed the effect of HR planning on the star hotel performance in Indonesia through the employee work productivity as the intervening variable was $Y = 0.019 + 2.021 = 2.040$. The relationship between the effect of HR organization on the star hotel performance in Indonesia through the employee work productivity as an intervening variable = $0.053 \times 0.105 \times 2.021 = 0.011$. This result indicated the effect of HR organizing on the star hotel performance in Indonesia through the employee work productivity as the intervening variable was $Y = 0.011 + 2.021 = 2.032$. The relationship between the effect of motivating the employees on the star hotel performance in Indonesia through the employee work productivity of as an intervening variable = $-0.022 \times (-0.003) \times 2.021 = 0.0001$. This result meant the effect of motivating the employees on star hotel performance in Indonesia through the employee work productivity as an intervening variable was $Y = 0.0001 + 2.021 = 2.021$. The relationship between the effect of work supervision on the star hotel performance in Indonesia through the employee work productivity as an intervening variable = $0.024 \times 0.274 \times 2.021 = 0.013$. This result showed the effect of work supervision on the star hotel performance in Indonesia through employee work productivity as the intervening variable was $Y = 0.013 + 2.021 = 2.034$. The indirect effect research results are presented in Table 15.

Table 15 Summary of Indirect Effect Research Results

No	The Relationship between Variables	Regression Coefficient Values	Positive/Negative Coefficient	Notes
1	The effect of HR planning on the work productivity of the star hotel performance in Indonesia and its impact on the star hotel performance in Indonesia	2.040	Positive	H ₁₀ was accepted
2	The effect of HR organizing on the work productivity of the star hotel performance in Indonesia and its impact on the star hotel performance in Indonesia	2.032	Positive	H ₁₀ was accepted
3	The effect of motivating the employees on the work productivity of the star hotel performance in Indonesia and its impact on the star hotel performance in Indonesia	2.021	Positive	H ₁₀ was rejected
4	The effect of work supervision on the work productivity of the star hotel performance in Indonesia and its impact on the star hotel performance in Indonesia	2.034	Positive	H ₁₀ was accepted

Source: Data Processing (SPSS), 2020

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the research analysis results, the researcher comprehensively concluded as follows: The HR planning offered had a positive and significant effect on the work productivity of the star hotel employees in Indonesia. HR organizing had a positive and significant effect on the work productivity of the star hotel employees in Indonesia. Motivating the employees had a negative effect on the work productivity of the star hotel employees in Indonesia. Work supervision to employees had a positive and significant effect on the work productivity of the star hotel employees in Indonesia. HR planning had a positive and significant effect on the star hotel performance in Indonesia. HR organizing had a positive and significant effect on the star hotel performance in Indonesia. Motivating the employees had a negative effect on the star hotel performance in Indonesia. Work supervision to employees had a positive and significant effect on the star hotel performance in Indonesia. Work productivity of star hotel employees in Indonesia had a positive and significant effect on the star hotel performance in Indonesia. HR planning, HR organizing, motivating the employees, and work supervision had a positive and significant effect on the star hotel performance in Indonesia through the work productivity of the star hotel employees in Indonesia.

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